

ELECTRONIC PAYMENT SYSTEMS AND THEIR LEGAL REGULATION

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Abstract. *The article is devoted to the analysis of electronic payment systems (EPS) and their legal regulation in modern conditions, with special emphasis on the situation in the Republic of Uzbekistan. The work examines the main aspects of the functioning of EPS, their development in the context of digitalization of the economy, as well as problems associated with legal regulation in this area. The key legislative initiatives and regulations governing the operation of electronic payments in Uzbekistan, as well as international approaches to regulating this industry, are described. The impact of innovative technologies, such as mobile payments and cryptocurrency payments, on the electronic payments market is analyzed, and existing risks associated with data security and financial crimes are identified. The article presents recommendations for improving legal regulation in order to ensure user safety and sustainable development of payment systems in the country.*

Keywords: *electronic payment systems, legal regulation, digital economy, fintech, cryptocurrencies, mobile payments, data security, Uzbekistan.*

Introduction

Electronic payment systems (EPS) have become an important part of the global economy over the past two decades, offering fast and affordable ways to conduct transactions for both individuals and businesses. These systems facilitate real-time transfers of funds between accounts, simplify access to financial services and promote the development of e-commerce. With the increase in the volume of non-cash transactions, the growth of digital technologies and the spread of mobile devices, the importance of EPS in the economies of countries and international trade has increased.

With the increasing use of electronic payments and the development of financial technologies, the importance of their legal regulation has also increased. The need for strict legislation is driven, in part, by the growing risks associated with cybersecurity and consumer protection. For example, according to the International Monetary Fund, global losses from cybercrime amount to approximately US\$1 trillion annually, a significant portion of which occurs in the financial sector according to McAfee [1]. In addition, according to the World Bank, electronic payments in developing countries increase the level of financial inclusion, helping to reduce poverty [2]. However, without an effective regulatory framework, these gains may be at risk.

The purpose of this article is to analyze the legislative regulation of electronic payment systems in the Republic of Uzbekistan, identify existing problems and propose measures to improve it. Particular attention will be paid to international regulatory experience in countries such as the European Union and Singapore to assess the applicability of these approaches in Uzbekistan.

Methods. The research used methods of literature analysis, content analysis and legislative analysis. The experiences of foreign countries that have successfully introduced laws on electronic payment systems into their legislation and their current effect were studied.

This study carried out a detailed analysis of the regulatory legal acts of Uzbekistan regulating the activities of electronic payment systems. The main attention is paid to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Payments and Payment Systems”, which is key in regulating the functioning of electronic payment systems in the country. It is important to note that this law regulates the rights and obligations of payment system participants, as well as requirements for operators [3]. Additionally, legislation related to the protection of personal data, including the Law “On the Protection of Personal Data”, was analyzed in order to understand how the security of information is ensured in the process of electronic transactions [4]. In addition, the relationship between such organizations and their clients is regulated by civil law.

For a deeper understanding of the regulation of electronic payment systems, a comparison was made with international standards and legislation. In particular, initiatives such as the European Union Directive 2015/2366/EU (PSD2), which regulates payment services and introduces new security and data protection standards for users, are considered. This directive is an important step in the development of e-commerce and payment systems at the EU level and in the world as a whole.

Another important example is regulation in Singapore, where there is a strict system of control over electronic payment operators and the active implementation of the latest technologies to ensure security and transparency of transactions. The application of such international standards allows us to assess what approaches can be adapted in Uzbekistan to improve the existing system.

Results

Today, in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the system of legal regulation of electronic payment systems (EPS) continues to develop. The central place in the legislation is occupied by the Law “On Payments and Payment Systems”, which was adopted in 2019 and has since been subject to several changes and additions. This law regulates relations between participants in payment systems, establishes requirements for their security and regulates the process of licensing operators.

In recent years, mobile payments, electronic wallets and systems related to cryptocurrencies have been actively developing in Uzbekistan. However, current legislation still does not fully regulate these new forms of financial transactions, which creates legal gaps and risks. According to information provided by the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the number of transactions in electronic payment systems is growing every year. In 2022, for example, the country's non-cash transactions increased by 35% compared to 2021, highlighting the trend toward accelerated adoption of technology in the financial sector. It is important to note that, despite the development of infrastructure and the introduction of new technologies, legal regulation often lags behind changes in practice [5].

According to statistics from the Central Bank, in recent years there has been a significant increase in the popularity of mobile and online payments in Uzbekistan. In particular, the number of users of remote servicing of bank accounts increased 1.5 times and reached 30 million as of January 1, 2023. At the same time, 1.2 million users are business entities, and the number of individuals using remote management systems for bank cards and bank deposit accounts amounted to 28.8 million.

In addition to the above, the QR-online system is also gaining popularity, which was launched to make instant payments using QR codes using mobile applications for goods and services using bank card funds without directly using a bank card and payment terminal. The

number of QR codes provided to businesses by the information system increased by only 8 thousand and amounted to 99 thousand units. Despite this, the volume of transactions made through this system increased from 14.9 billion soums in 2021 to 191.6 billion soums in 2022, and the number increased 4.2 times and reached 63.2 thousand units. [5].

However, the increase in transaction volume also leads to an increase in fraud and unauthorized transactions. According to the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Uzbekistan, the number of registered cases of fraud in the field of electronic payments in 2022 increased by 15%, which emphasizes the need for enhanced data protection and increased reliability of electronic payment systems. Despite this, the legal framework for combating such crimes is not yet fully developed, and measures to prevent financial crimes are often insufficient.

One of the main challenges identified in the study is the need to update legislation to ensure compliance with rapidly evolving technologies and financial products. In particular:

- At the moment, in Uzbekistan there is a general legislative framework for the protection of personal data, however, in the context of EPS, the requirements for information protection in practice are not always properly observed. This is especially true for mobile and online payments, where the threats of data leaks and cybercrimes are becoming increasingly relevant;

- with the legislation of Uzbekistan does not yet sufficiently regulate modern technologies such as cryptocurrencies and blockchain. These technologies, despite their active use in the global financial sector, are not properly reflected in national legislation;

- In the context of globalization of financial markets, there is a need to coordinate the legislation of countries to ensure the protection and security of electronic payments. In Uzbekistan, the system of cooperation with other states and international financial organizations is not yet sufficiently developed, which makes it difficult to protect national interests in the field of e-commerce.

There are a number of positive changes that have been observed in recent years. Such as:

- increasing the level of security, i.e., the Central Bank of Uzbekistan has introduced new requirements for EPS operators aimed at improving the security of transactions. This includes mandatory use of data protection standards as well as fraud prevention measures;

- development of infrastructure for mobile payments, i.e., mobile payments and electronic wallets are actively developing in Uzbekistan, which improves access to financial services for the wider population. This helps to increase financial inclusion and reduce the level of cash payments;

- attracting foreign investment, i.e., in recent years, the country has been opening up new opportunities for international EPS operators, which helps improve the quality of services and increase the competitiveness of the national financial sector.

Discussion and conclusions

The legal framework governing electronic payment systems in Uzbekistan has played an important role in ensuring stability and confidence in the financial sector. The adopted Law “On Payments and Payment Systems” and other regulations create the basis for the functioning of electronic payment systems, establishing the rights and obligations of participants. This strengthens the market position, promotes the development of new financial products and increases the confidence of citizens and businesses in non-cash payments.

One of the key success factors is proper licensing and control by the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan. This not only ensures transaction security but also prevents various financial crimes such as fraud and money laundering. The laws contribute to the development of

financial inclusion, which in turn leads to an increase in the volume of non-cash payments, confirming the positive impact of legal regulation on the country's economy.

Despite regulatory progress, there are a number of significant challenges that require attention.

The rapid development of financial technologies and the emergence of new forms of payment systems, such as cryptocurrencies and blockchain, challenge legislative bodies to quickly respond to new threats and opportunities. The current legal approach does not always keep pace with changes in the market and is often insufficient to manage innovation in the field of EPS.

With the growing number of users of electronic payment systems, the threat of personal data leaks and cyber-attacks increases. Cybercrime is becoming increasingly sophisticated and to curb it, it is necessary to implement modern security measures such as multi-level authentication, encryption and other technologies to protect customer transactions and data.

Uzbekistan should take into account international best practices and adapt best practices, creating conditions for the growth of innovative financial technologies, while simultaneously addressing security and data protection issues.

The Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan plays a key role in regulating and controlling EPS. It monitors compliance with legislation, licenses payment systems, develops regulations and monitors their implementation. However, it is important to note that in light of new challenges such as digital currencies and blockchain technologies, the role of the Central Bank must be expanded. It should not only regulate traditional payment systems, but also develop new approaches to regulating cryptocurrencies and other digital assets.

In addition, the Central Bank should strengthen its efforts to ensure transaction security by introducing new standards and approaches to data protection, including the use of modern technologies to prevent cyber threats.

With the development of EPS, many new risks appear, including for financial security. Cybercrimes such as phishing, hacking of bank accounts and the use of cryptocurrencies for money laundering remain the main threats. In this regard, it is necessary to strengthen control over operations, conduct regular security audits and develop a system for protecting customer data. Uzbekistan should actively cooperate with international organizations such as the FATF to implement effective measures against financial crimes, as well as develop legislative initiatives to control cryptocurrencies and digital assets.

With the introduction of EPS, consumer habits are changing. Users are increasingly choosing mobile payments over traditional payment methods, increasing their convenience and security. This trend is fueling an accelerated shift to cashless transactions, an important step towards financial inclusion. In turn, this creates new opportunities for small and medium-sized enterprises, expanding their access to payment systems and improving financial inclusion for the population.

In the country's economy, EPS is driving the growth of digital financial services such as mobile banking and e-wallets, which also has an impact on the labor market, creating new jobs in the financial technology sector.

Modern technologies such as blockchain and cryptocurrencies provide new opportunities for the development of financial services, but at the same time create new legal and regulatory problems. For example, cryptocurrencies do not have central control and can be used for illegal activities such as money laundering and terrorist financing. Uzbekistan needs to develop

legislation regulating the use of cryptocurrencies and other digital assets in order to prevent possible risks and increase the transparency of financial transactions. Another important step will be the creation of a regulatory body that will be able to control activities in the field of blockchain technologies and cryptocurrencies.

Government initiatives aimed at digitalizing the economy play an important role in the development of EPS. For example, active support for start-ups and the creation of government programs for the digitalization of financial services stimulate the growth of innovative projects in the field of electronic financial services. However, for further development, it is necessary to continue to improve the infrastructure for electronic payments, including strengthening connections with international payment systems and creating incentives for the introduction of new technologies.

In addition, to improve legal regulation, it is important to maintain active dialogue between government agencies and the private sector in order to adapt legislation to rapidly changing technological conditions.

Legal regulation of electronic payment systems in Uzbekistan represents an important aspect in the development of the country's financial infrastructure. Despite significant regulatory progress, there are many problems and challenges that require attention and proactive solutions. Uzbekistan must continue to improve legislation, taking into account international trends and developing technologies, as well as strengthen the security and protection of user data. Ultimately, the creation of an effective and secure legal framework for electronic payment systems will ensure the sustainable development of the financial system and increase public confidence in digital payment technologies.

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